

The influence of temperature on the stability of polymer foam cored sandwich structures

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1 Introduction

Polymer foam cored sandwich structures are frequently exposed to elevated temperatures. For example, a temperature of 85°C has been recorded on the surface of wind turbine blades [1]. The elevated temperatures induce significant degradation of the mechanical properties of polymer foams [2]. Furthermore, a temperature gradient may be introduced through the thickness of the core if only one face sheet is exposed to a heat source such as with solar radiation, thereby imparting inhomogeneous mechanical properties to the polymer foam in the through thickness direction. The overall structural performance of the sandwich structure suffers from thermally induced degradation of the core. Analytical models [3, 4] have predicted a change in the mechanical behaviour from linear and stable to nonlinear and unstable due to the loss of core stiffness at elevated temperatures. Although this prediction has not been experimentally validated, it has aroused concerns on the performance of sandwich structures at elevated temperatures. Thereby, a detailed experimental study is required to confirm the thermomechanical interaction effects.

The work presented in the present paper comprises an experimental investigation on the influence of elevated temperatures on the stability of sandwich structures. Initial tests were conducted with sandwich beams subjected to a simultaneous three-point bending and a through thickness temperature gradient, *i.e.* the same arrangement as in [3]. Infrared thermography (IRT) was used to obtain the temperature field and digital image correlation (DIC) to obtain full-field specimen deformation. It was

shown that localised indentation resulting in material failure was the only failure mode achievable in the three-point bending configuration. Hence, a four-point bending configuration was adopted. This had the added benefit of allowing a uniform temperature across the specimen length near the mid-span. A high-speed camera was used to view the development and evolution of face sheet wrinkles. A shift of the specimen failure mode from face sheet yielding to wrinkling is observed as the specimen is exposed to rising temperatures.

2 Experimental investigations using three-point bending

2.1 Experimental arrangement

The three-point bending configuration is shown in Fig. 1. Sandwich beam specimens were made using a 25 mm thick PVC foam core (Divinycell H100, Sweden) and a 0.9 mm thick aluminum alloy face sheet (AA6082-T6). The temperature dependence of the elastic properties on the Divinycell H100 has been investigated in [2, 5], which shows that at 90°C there is more than a 50% reduction in the room temperature elastic modulus. Aluminium alloy was selected as the face sheet material because of its large heat conductivity and because that its stiffness and strength are virtually independent of temperature over the range applicable in the current work. A long support span of 450 mm was initially selected to eliminate specimen failures by core shear yielding.

The elevated temperature was introduced by heating the upper surface of the specimen using an infrared (IR) lamp, while maintaining the lower face sheet at

ambient temperature. To reduce the width-wise temperature gradient, insulation in the form of additional PVC foam was placed on both sides of the specimen. To assess the temperature distribution through the core thickness, images of the specimen side were collected by a Cedip Silver 480M IR detector. A linear temperature profile through the core thickness was observed [6].

The mechanical load was introduced using a servo-hydraulic test machine *via* a 12 mm diameter steel roller in the centre. The mechanical bending load was applied after the specimen had been heated to a steady state. Before measuring the deformation it is necessary to remove the foam insulation from the side of the beam under observation by the camera. The bending load was applied by moving the actuator at a rate of 20 mm/minute so that during the test the temperature gradient through the core thickness remained close to as linear as possible.

Fig. 1: (a) loading configuration of the three-point bending experiment; (b) experimental arrangement.

The specimen deformation was assessed using digital image correlation (DIC [7]). As the specimen

was loaded, images of the specimen side surface were captured with a 5 mega pixel LA Vision VC-imager E-lite digital camera (with a frame rate of 2 Hz) fitted with a 105 mm Sigma lens. The side of the specimen was sprayed with random black and white paint to form speckles for facilitating image correlation. The DIC algorithm tracks the movement of the speckles relative to a reference image, hence providing a full-field assessment of the specimen deformation. Images were recorded synchronously with the load data, and the image captured at zero load was used as the reference image. The image correlation was conducted in subsets with a size of 64×64 pixels. The displacement accuracy was verified as about 0.02 pixel by performing image correlation between two images at zero load. A typical z direction (through thickness) displacement field obtained using DIC is shown in Figure 3. It is seen that the largest displacement occurs at the mid-span, and the displacement decreases symmetrically towards the two ends of the specimen.

Fig. 2: A displacement field obtained by DIC in the elastic region.

The test procedure was defined as follows:

1. The sandwich specimen was positioned on the three-point bending jig. The white light camera was positioned to record the specimen side images. The insulation foam blocks were positioned.
2. The top face sheet of the specimen was heated to a required temperature and held until a steady temperature state was achieved, established by thermocouple readings from the top face sheet.
3. The insulation was removed on one side to enable images of the specimen deformation to be obtained.
4. The load was applied in displacement control at a rate of 20 mm/min until the specimen failed.

Images of the specimen side surface and the load (P) were recorded at 2 Hz.

2.2 Test results and discussion

A set of tests was conducted where the top face sheet of the specimens was held at 25°C, 50°C, 70°C and 90°C, and the deflection of the top face sheet at the mid-span was measured using DIC. The load-deflection curves are shown in Fig. 3(a). All the load-deflection curves start with a linear trend. The gradient of the curve reduces as the top face sheet temperature increases. This is due to the loss of the core shear modulus at elevated temperatures resulting in a larger shear deflection. Indentation is accompanied by a reduction in load where the core is crushed followed by face-core debonding, as depicted in Fig. 3(b). A comparison between the prediction from a geometrically nonlinear but material linear elastic FE model and the experimental results is shown in Fig. 4; full details of the FE model is given in [8]. The linear part of the load-deflection curves derived by the FE model agrees well with the corresponding experimental results. The load-deflection curve obtained by FE extends to the stage that load-deflection gradually becomes nonlinear, indicating the occurrence of the localised buckling of the top face sheet at the mid-span (eventually leading to instability for core and face materials with infinite straining capability). It is clearly shown that the nonlinear behaviour predicted by the HSAPT model (driven by geometric nonlinearity combined with a reduction of core stiffness with increasing temperature), is in all cases preceded by the indentation with core compressive yielding (plasticity). For this particular specimen, the failure load by localised indentation is approximately 1/5 of the load that triggers localised buckling. To provoke the localised buckling it would be necessary to increase the support span of the current sandwich beam specimen by over 5 times. In this case the value of P that triggers the indentation remains the same but the value of P provoking the localised buckling is 5 times smaller, thus the predicted localised buckling may be experimentally observed. However, manufacturing sandwich beam specimens with such a large aspect ratio is difficult and testing would require a bespoke facility.

Fig. 3: Test results. (a) load-deflection of sandwich beam specimens tested at different temperatures; (b) image of indentation zone in a typical failed sandwich beam specimen

Fig. 4: Top face sheet load-deflection curves comparing experimental and elastic FE results.

An alternative approach which can provoke the loss of stability using practically sized sandwich beam specimens is to introduce a distributed transverse pressure load rather than the concentrated transverse load. In this case, a large bending moment can be generated for the specimen without the indentation. The distributed pressure could be introduced by

using loading pads such as rubber blocks positioned between the loading rollers and the specimen surfaces. However, the loading pad would mask the central heating zone which is the location of interest (i.e. at the mid-span).

Therefore it was decided to adopt a four-point bending configuration, as the beam section near the mid-span is theoretically subjected to a pure bending with a uniform bending moment. Thereby, the localised buckling should occur in the region between the loading points. The transverse load can be introduced through loading pads and the shape of the pressure load underneath the loading pad does not exert a significant influence on the bending behaviour of the specimen near the mid-span, thus an accurate characterization of pressure load underneath the loading pad is not required. Additionally, introducing a uniform elevated temperature across the face sheet near the mid-span is very convenient as the heat radiation from an infrared lamp is not masked by any parts of the four-point bending jig.

3 Experimental investigation using four-point bending

3.1 Experimental arrangement

The loading configuration and photograph of the four-point bending experiment are shown in Fig. 2. The specimen material is similar as that used in the three-point bending test except here the face sheets are made from aluminium alloy AA7075-T6 which has a larger yield strength enabling a specimen to be designed, where wrinkling occurred before face sheet yielding, that fitted the size limitations of a standard test machine. The specimen was also designed with a large aspect ratio to eliminate core shear failure. The length of the specimen was selected to be 600 mm. The thickness of the face sheet and core were chosen to be 0.3 mm and 15 mm, respectively. The width was chosen as 50 mm which is 3.2 times the beam thickness and 1/12 of the beam length, thus a near uniform beam flexure through the width is guaranteed. The loading span L_1 and L_2 were chosen to be 275 mm and 100 mm, respectively. To avoid localised indentation, loading pads composed of a 6 mm thick rubber block and 1 mm thick aluminum face were used to distribute the

loads on the top face sheet (see insert in Fig. 5(b)). The pads were firmly bonded on the top face sheet of the specimen using the adhesive Araldite 2000. The specimen was heated in the same way as for the three-point bending and a linear temperature gradient through the core thickness was also observed. Tests were conducted with the top face sheet temperature held at 25°C, 50°C, 70°C, 80°C and 90°C, and DIC was used to assess the deformation measurement. To capture face sheet wrinkles, a PHOTRON FASTCAM SA5 camera with a frame rate frequency of 60 kHz was used.

Fig. 5: Four-point bending experiment. (a) loading configuration; (b) actual set-up.

3.2 Test Results and discussion

Specimens tested at all temperatures failed by a sudden collapse, where the core near the mid-span was locally crushed accompanied by the face sheet folding into the core, as shown in Fig. 6(a). The measured load-deflection curves are shown in Fig. 6(b), where the horizontal axis represents the deflection of the top face sheet at the mid-span and the vertical axis represents the load P . The legend

shows the top and bottom face sheet temperatures for each test. Fig. 6(b) shows that the overall stiffness reduces with the increase of the top face sheet temperature. This is as expected because at elevated temperatures the shear deflection is larger due to the reduction in the core shear modulus value. Similarly, the maximum load also decreases with rising temperatures and the reduction is very significant between 70°C and 90°C.

A comparison between the experimental values and analytical predictions with respect to the failure load is shown in Fig. 7, which shows the stress of the top face sheet at the failure load against temperature of the top face sheet. The blue line represents the yield strength of the aluminium face sheet that was experimentally obtained by tensile tests. The red line represents the critical wrinkling stress obtained by a modification of Plantama's wrinkling analysis [9]. Fig. 7 shows a good agreement between the experiments and analytical predictions, where the specimen failure is initiated by face sheet yielding at 25°C, 50°C but by face sheet wrinkling (instability) at temperatures higher than 70°C.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6: (a) Final failure shape of the specimen; (b) load-deflection curve of sandwich beam specimen at different temperatures

Fig. 7: Comparison between the predicted failure stresses and the experimental results

To further examine the occurrence of face sheet wrinkling for the specimen tested at 70°C and 90°C, high-speed imaging was used to observe the face sheet wrinkling wave prior to the collapse of the core. Images of the specimen deformation were recorded using the PHOTRON FASTCAM SA5 camera at a frame rate of 60 kHz. DIC was conducted on these images to obtain the full field displacement of the specimen to assess the failure progress. Fig. 8 shows the specimen displacement in the z direction at the initiation of the specimen failure, which is overlaid on an image of the specimen. Here, the image collected just ($17\mu s$) before the image shown in Fig. 8(a) is defined at time 0, as no inhomogeneous or wavy deformation was observed. The images shown in Fig. 8(a) and Fig. 8(b) are the next two that were captured at $17\mu s$ and $34\mu s$, respectively. The z direction displacement map clearly shows that the specimen failure started from triggering a wavy deformation of the top face sheet.

The magnitude of the wavy displacement of the top face sheet is plotted in Fig. 9. It is observed that, at $17\mu s$, the displacement of the top face sheet was in a very regularly sinusoidal shape, which indicates that the face sheet buckled and the deformation was still in the material elastic region. However, at $34\mu s$, the wavy displacement of the top face sheet became very irregular, where the magnitude at the wave crest is much larger than the wave trough. This indicates that core crushing occurred underneath the face sheet at the position of wave crest due to the large z direction compressive stress resulting from the wavy deformation of the face sheet. The core

crushing was then followed by the face sheet failure by folding into the core which results in a total collapse of the beam specimen, as shown in Fig. 6(a). Hence, the wavy deformation of the face sheet which represents the occurrence of wrinkling was successfully observed using high-speed imaging combined with DIC. The wavy deformation triggered a very quick core crushing (within tens of μs) and this makes high-speed imaging essential for capturing the wrinkling behaviour.

Fig. 8: z direction displacement contour of the specimen at time $17\mu\text{s}$ and $34\mu\text{s}$.

Fig. 9: z direction displacement of the top face sheet at time $17\mu\text{s}$ and $34\mu\text{s}$.

The face sheet wavy deformation shown in Fig. 8 was not only observed for the specimens tested at

70°C , 80°C and 90°C , but also for the specimens tested at 25°C and 50°C . However, this does not contradict the prediction shown in Fig. 7 that the specimen failure at 25°C and 50°C should be initiated by face sheet yielding. This is because when yielding occurs in the face sheet there is a significant reduction in stiffness which in turn provokes the wrinkling instability. To confirm this hypothesis, the compressive strain of the top face sheet just before the specimen collapse was measured. Image correlation was conducted on the images recorded through the entire loading process by the LA Vision VC-imager E-lite digital camera. As the compressive strain of the top face sheet over the span L_I is theoretically uniform, the average x direction strain over a length of 50 mm near mid-span was obtained for a better strain precision. The stress-strain states of the top face sheet of sandwich beam specimens before collapse are marked by the triangular symbols in Fig. 10. The curves in Fig. 10 are from tensile tests on the aluminium face sheet tested at different temperatures. It is assumed that the compressive behaviour of the aluminium alloy is identical to the tensile behaviour. Therefore for a convenient comparison, the compressive stress and strain of the face sheet are shown as positive in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: The stress-strain state of the face-sheet of sandwich beam specimens before core collapse

From Fig. 10, it can be clearly seen that for the specimen tested at 25°C , the top face sheet has yielded before the specimen collapse. For the specimens tested at 70°C and 90°C , the top face sheet is still in the linear deformation region when the specimen collapses, which indicates the specimen failure is triggered by wrinkling

(instability). For the specimen tested at 50°C, before specimen collapse the top face sheet has yielded but by a very small amount, hence 50°C is near to the temperature where the failure mode of the specimen shifts from face sheet yielding to wrinkling. All these observations agree very well with the failure mode prediction as shown in Fig. 7.

4 Conclusions

The influence of elevated temperatures on the stability of polymer foam cored sandwich structures has been studied experimentally using both three-point bending and four-point bending loading configurations. High-speed imaging combined with DIC was used to capture the onset of wrinkling. It was demonstrated that:

1. The typical three-point bending configuration with concentrated transverse load causes localised indentation due to the material plasticity rather than the elastic instability in the form of localised buckling of the face sheet as predicted in [3]. However, particular attention needs to be paid on the elastic instability if the sandwich beam specimen has a very large length to thickness aspect ratio.
2. By using a four-point bending configuration with distributed pressure load, the wrinkling of sandwich beam specimens at elevated temperatures was provoked. Only one wrinkle was observed using high-speed imaging and DIC. The wrinkle triggers the core and face sheet yielding and following that total collapse of the sandwich beam in tens of μ s.
3. For the particular sandwich beam specimen, the failure mode shifts from face sheet yielding to wrinkling at 58°C. The failure load by wrinkling at 90°C is about 30% less than the failure load by face sheet yielding at room temperature. Thereby, the thermomechanical interaction effects in polymer foam cored sandwich structures should be implemented in relevant design and analysis.

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